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Methods of the Seafloor Survey

南海海域海湾调查研究现状

Analysis of the Marine Survey of the South China Sea

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Chapter 1. Investigation means. National and local government survey research plan. Planning of national research studies

Recently, Government of the People's Republic of China maintains all multi-dimensional aspects of the development of the marine geology program around South China Sea area. A cross-institutional arrangement can impact on the ocean governance through their elements in various ways. Thus, as an interdisciplinary science having deep links between geology and oceanography, it should include the exploitation and protection of ocean environment and resources, marine economy, ocean policy, marine regulation and ocean management, the application and resources of marine science and new technology, development of system of ports and coastal engineering.

Various methods have been developed for successful application at the depths of the ocean seafloor of the continental margins using not only underwater photography, but also underwater acoustic methods. These methods have been applied towards studies of the South China Sea region. For instance, to the eastern tropical part of the Pacific ocean was recently surveyed in the scope of a program for studying distribution of the ferromanganese clusters located at the seafloor basement, carried out at depths from 4400 to 5100 m with the use of a 1-5 m above the bottom of installed underwater cameras.

Surrounded by seas to the west, south, and east, China is a maritime nation. Therefore, development of the marine geology program on the governmental level is highly actual for this state. Proper development of the marine geology program on the governmental level has started successfully and continues developing. Planning and organization of the geological research and survey is conducted by the Ministry of Geology. The regional departments through territorial geological management and geological agencies, ministries related to development of mineral resources and construction. Scientific work in marine geology is carried out by multiple research

centers, institutes and laboratories and of some other ministries and Chinese Academy of Sciences. A series of periodic scientific geological journals reporting marine expedition results and outcomes published regularly with the most important publishing house located in Beijing. Since 1960s People's Republic of China is intensively developing the geology of the South China Sea seabed and ocean floor investigations, with particular focus of industrial mineral development of the large areas of the continental shelf. The geophysical methods are widely used in research of the geology of the seafloor. Recently, high-latitude drilling is being performed with a specially equipped vessels.

Fig. 1. South China Sea. Mapping: QGIS 3.0. Large territory, dense population, vast natural resources of the People's Republic of China and at the same time a long

coastline determine the importance of the marine spaces and resources for this country. Therefore, the government realized the scale of the problem and initiated the creation of the marine geology centers in the country. The organization of geological research in the international scale and discussion of the most important problems of the marine geology is regularly performed at the International Geological Congresses. Currently, China has extensive and special interest in the coastal areas and marine geologic investigations. In order to realize these benefits and change the adverse situation of backwardness, it has taken many active measures in the South China Sea scientific research.

In the South China Sea, continuous efforts have been made by the government of China to explore hydrocarbon in the concession blocks. Thus, attempts have been made by the Chinese Institute of Geology projects since early 1960s to obtain data on the geological structure of the shallow portions of the South China Sea. Questions on the geologic structure and tectonics, stratigraphy and sequence stratigraphy, sedimentary facies and processes, and the origin and development of the seas around the South China Sea include shelf areas with a narrow continental shelf and deep basins, and the South China Sea with numerous rocky embayment [1], [19], [37]. These all were recently investigated by the Chinese authorities. Special research projects have been investigated marine geological structure drilled holes throughout the South China Sea basins. Shallow subsurface mapping using high-frequency profiling and deep cores into the Holocene/Pleistocene boundary have been made to reveal late Quaternary depositional processes and sequence stratigraphy in this unique epicontinental sea [25], [30], [31].

The geology of the South China Sea is well described in numerous reports. The southern coast of the China is characterized by numerous postglacial embayments and near shore islands. Sedimentation is controlled largely by moderate tidal currents depositing fine-grained sediments. South Sea is characterized by numerous islands that have been submerged during the last transgression. Shallow subsurface mapping using high-resolution seismic profiling has revealed that the sea is characterized by

complex incised valley systems and transgressive deposits during the rise in sea level. This is an area for further detailed studies of high-resolution and high accuracy sequence stratigraphy. A number of offshore exploratory wells have also been drilled by the Chinese governmental companies, revealing high hydrocarbon potential.

The most important and evident trend in the recent development of the Chinese marine geology policy is advanced made in research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry. This included following activities: 1) supported research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry; 2) supported research on ocean and polar science and technology policies and institutions; 3) fostering of outstanding professionals in the marine sector and public services; 4) development, inspection, and repair of marine-related equipment, machinery and technology; 5) establishment and operation of marine infrastructure, such as marine science research stations. Funded research, and technology partnerships with domestic and overseas universities focused on marine geology, other research institutions, and companies which resulted in a variety of published research on China South Sea geology, e.g. [24], [34], [35], [29], [36]. The ocean governance, currently run by Chinese government, includes four essential elements, such as ocean policy, institutional arrangement to set up and implement ocean policy, coordination and cooperation between or among sectors, and the constituency for the policy

Among the most famous Government run ocean research center of the South China are: State Key Laboratory of Satellite Ocean Environment Dynamics-SOED, Second Institute of Oceanography SOA, Hangzhou, South China Sea Institute Of Oceanology, Xiamen, China Ocean Development Research Center (Qingdao), Chinese Academy of Sciences Institute of Oceanology. These centers have driven development of the marine sciences and technology of China for several decades years since their establishment. Ocean centers and research institutes of China have

several branches located within the country, all of them fulfill necessary functions in marine geology research and development.

Brain marine research center in the field of maritime geology is the Hangzhou Second Institute of Oceanography SOA. The Chinese CAS approved a bill to establish a research center to help advance the country's marine geology sector. Several publications have been published with a focus on the China marine geology in the study area: [4], [6], [13], [27], [33]. The scope of this research activities is also quite wide: from the study of the marine environment to shipbuilding. State decisions in the field of maritime activities (administrative, legislative reform, etc.) are taken on the basis of the results of operations of this body. A wide range of fisheries research is carried out at the fisheries centers and branches [15], [16]. The most progressive tool used in marine geology seafloor investigations is multi-beam techniques.

Multibeam Echosounder and Sonar Overview

Fig. 2. Types of the echo-sounder devices. Image source:

www.whitepapers.marinetechologynews.com

Due to the multi-beam echo-sounder precise surveying the main features of the study

of the seafloor in recent years is represented by a complex detailed geological and geophysical surveys. For decades, the study of the structure of the ocean floor was conducted along the ship by route measurement. Large distances between the ticks did not allow to correlate data with a high degree of reliability. As a result of the recent research progress, all types of oceanic morphostructures of the World Ocean were detected and discovered. Large forms of underwater relief (such as mid-oceanic ridges, uplands, plateaus, gutters, fault zones, etc.) were discovered as well as smaller ones, such as separate mountains, underwater canals. The details of the study significantly improved after the organization of work on landfills – limited areas within which parallel tracks are located at the distances of 2-5 miles.

Fig. 3. Principle of the echo-sounder device. Image source: British Antarctic Survey.

The use of multi-beam echo sounders resulted in full (or almost complete) coverage of the world Ocean floor mapping. A survey of the bottom at the

current level should include a set of such equipment as a multi-beam echo sounder, profiler, magnetometer, gravimeter, side-scan sonar, and continuous seismic profiling. Studies of the landforms are usually accompanied by the station research (collecting various geophysical data). As the ship follows a planned straight line over the area to be mapped, the transducers send multiple sound pulses to the sea floor. These pulses are sent in many directions at one time. When the pulses hit the sea floor, they will reflect back to the ship and be detected by the receiver. The multibeam system then calculates the angle, the time it took for the pulses to travel, the ship's orientation to the water to determine the depth of the seafloor at that spot. Once the data pulses return and are analyzed by the computer, topography maps of the seafloor can be created. To "ground-truth" the mapping data divers or remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) are used to verify the data collected on board the ship. Navigation is an important goal of ensuring the safety of conducting marine survey, marine geological and geophysical research. Currently, the main method of determining the location of the vessel is a global system of satellite navigation and GPS positioning. A large number of satellites enable to locate vessels, including submarines, up to meters away, regardless of the location of the work area.

The study of the ocean floor is possible not only through vessels, but by means of satellites from space. Systematic measurement of the surface height (altimetry) of the world ocean water level by the satellite radar at an altitude of about 800 km with an accuracy of several meters, proved that water level depends on the topography of the ocean floor and density of the underlying rocks. In other words, the positive forms of relief attract the water body increasing the height of its surface, and *vice versa*. The figurative concept of "world ocean level" is not permanent, and the differences in the height of the water surface can be more than a hundred meters. Analysis of the ocean altimetric data enabled to create a mathematical model of the relief of the entire oceans, the so-called predicted topography with a high degree of reliability. Satellite data were compared with real echo sounder measurements and extrapolated to unexplored regions.

Among other research techniques currently used by Chinese researchers for the seafloor surveying and mapping is the UUV. The unmanned underwater vehicles (UUV), sometimes known as underwater drones, are any vehicles that are able to operate underwater without a human occupant. The UUV are used to solve the problem of fundamental science and purely practical tasks (inspection of underwater parts of engineering structures, pipelines, etc.). In the deep ocean (for instance, trenches), they are used to test the rocks of the bottom, direct observations of the geological structure, collection of information about the pelagic world, benthos or the properties of the aquatic environment. Using UUV apparatus a breakdown of the oceanic crust on the transverse ridge in the Atlantic ocean discovered. Underwater manned vehicles widely used to study active and inactive hydrothermal fields. The UUV vehicles may be divided into two categories, remotely operated underwater vehicles (ROVs), which are controlled by a remote human operator, and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), which operate independently of direct human input. The latter category would constitute a kind of robot. The accuracy of the predicted topography enabled to plan marine expedition paths (choose areas, tracks), to make major theoretical generalizations. However, it should be emphasized that it cannot completely replace the echo-sounder *in-situ* surveying.

Chapter 2. Investigation of research results: the main research progress and analysis of key results

Currently, Chinese governmental research plan of marine geology includes following tasks in the development of the marine geology program around the South China Sea: To perform applied research to promote the efficient use of coastal and ocean resources; To undertake comprehensive surveys and studies of South China Sea and open oceans; To conduct scientific research in polar and tropical regions, especially in Antarctica and the south Pacific; To develop technologies related to the coastal and harbor engineering, ships and ocean engineering, and maritime safety; To support and cooperate with other government agencies, universities and private

industries towards the development of marine resources and the protection of the ocean environment; To coordinate and participate in the international cooperation concerning oceanographic research projects. Research interests of CAS, Guangzhou as a major research center for marine geology in China encompass the area surrounding the South China Sea and the region of the western Pacific Ocean (e.g. Mariana Trench). However, it also include fundamental research in Antarctica. The main areas of interest are geological and geophysical science, the life sciences, and climate science. The Chinese Academy of Sciences owns the research vessels R/V, used to supply the year-round ocean investigations.

Systematic ocean exploration in the 20th century started on the ships, naval or merchant navies of different countries. However, the diversity of scientific tasks and the need to study completely different objects both in the water column and on the ocean floor led to the creation of the specialized geological and geophysical vessels, which were installed, as well as different equipment and tools. Generally, the ocean scientific research fleet consists of vessels of various state and departmental affiliation. They were designed for specialized study of the seabed relief, the biological and geological resources of the ocean, geophysical fields, multilateral study of the properties of the ocean water column and the nearby atmosphere layers. Special units of the scientific fleet are drilling vessels and drilling platforms, as well as underwater manned vehicles.

Seismic methods in the ocean floor exploration are the most important ones to study the structure of the sedimentary cover of ocean or its deeper horizons (structure, velocity characteristics, etc): [14], [17], [18], [11]. Depending on the frequency of the radiation, the depth of the penetration energy into the sedimentary cover or deeper horizons may change. High-frequency single-channel (continuous seismic profiling) multi-channel methods, as well as deep seismic sounding can be distinguished by the frequency of radiation.

The principle of the seismic method of seafloor survey is based on the penetration of the energy issued by the compressed air, electric discharge, into the

water column and then into the rock. After reflection of the signal from the sedimental horizons, the reflected signal goes back to the ship and is received by the special antenna (the seismic streamer). The received data is accumulated digitally on a seismic station. Further processing is completed on the computer stations by a variety of software programs that filter out the acoustic noises and store useful information about the structure of the earth's crust. There are many modifications of the equipment (such as bottom stations, radio beacons, etc.).

Research facilities of the South China Sea Institute of Oceanology Hangzhou widely use towed devices above the bottom (for example, a set of equipment designed to study gravimetric, magnetic fields, together with a lateral-view sonar, profiling and other geological and geophysical equipment. Special immersible robot is mixed over the ocean floor at an altitude of 300-400 m. The side-scan sonars are designed to study the morphology of the bottom, identify faults in the oil pipelines, search for sunken objects (e.g. ships) of almost any size with a high degree of resolution. The principle of their operation is based on irradiation of the bottom surface with a frequency of about 6.5 kHz.

For the practical geological reasons there are a variety of the developed methods to study the seafloor. Thus, testing of bottom rocks through the rocks extraction from the ocean floor is being used by use of various tools such as tubes, dredges, pipes, trawls, scoops, etc. Tube testing is primarily intended to study the upper (up to 50 m) layers of the sedimentary cover pressed by its own weight. The tube penetrates at a high speed to the ocean bottom and takes a column of the seafloor sediments into the hollow part of the instrument. In some cases even the bedrock may be taken as well. Although a complete section of oceanic crust has not yet been drilled, geologists have several pieces of evidence that help them understand the ocean floor. The some of them are the samples recovered from the ocean floor by dredging and drilling. Dredging is an underwater rock excavation. It is one of the main methods that allows to take samples of the bedrock from any depths. Dredging can be carried out at depths from 20 to 6000 m.

Chapter 3. Major issues: important issues of concern at home and abroad

Analysis of the development trends

Survey technical means and equipment at South China Sea Institute of Oceanology include modern apparatuses and drilling equipment. The applied methods are high-resolution airborne geophysical surveying, land magnetic and resistivity surveying, the natural electrical field method, induced polarization and transient electromagnetic techniques, as well as gravity surveying [32], [20]. It conducts integrated mapping of the coastal environment and marine geology to define offshore hazards and sediment processes around China, support habitat and resource management, and monitor change, etc.

Coastal and marine geology expertise, run by the Chinese government, also contributes to the environmental mission of China, thus providing impartial information on the health of marine ecosystems and environment around Hainan and Taiwan Islands, the natural hazards (tsunami), natural resources, impacts of the climate change, and the core science systems that help scientists provide timely, relevant, as well as usable information. Institutional arrangement is both critical and essential element in ocean governance. Therefore, through the cross-institutional arrangement within China, marine geology research and survey laboratories began to make efforts for the establishment of integrated ocean policy such as introduction of new legal action, policy strategy, or comprehensive planning systems.

The question of the depth of the ocean has long attracted researchers [3], [20], [28], [22], [26]. The bathymetry of the ocean floor reflects plate tectonics processes, including trench movement, deformation and bending which is associated with mantle convection at the global scale [21]. There are three classified types of the continental tectonic plate boundaries producing a unique type of the seafloor bathymetry. To measure depth of the ocean first various tenches and a metal cable were used. These methods of measurement could not be considered as accurate and of course led to major errors, which contributed to the map errors.

Acoustic systems (echo sounders) of seafloor survey appeared before the 1950s. This was a revolutionary breakthrough in the practice of studying the ocean, since sounders allowed to build a continuous profile of the bottom relief along the measurement line. The principle of operation of the sounders is to send an audio signal, which is reflected from the acoustically rigid surface of the bottom and returns to the receiving antenna. The speed of sound in the oceans can vary from 1400 to 1550 m/s. The maximum speed is timed to the depths of 1200-1300 m. The way passes a very long distances without loss of energy. Multiplying the speed of the acoustic noise in the water by the time gives seafloor depth. The accuracy of such measurement is impacted by the water properties: temperature, salinity, and so on. The difference in the speed of the sound for depths up to 200 m reaches 3-4 m/s and for depths up to 800 m to 1-1.5 m/s. Therefore, for each specific area before taking the ocean floor depth measurements it is required to carry out special measurements that give a curve of change of speed of sound in water which allows to make the appropriate amendments.

Fig.4. Measurements of various types of the seafloor sediments. Image source: <http://www3.kutztown.edu/JOCMS2011/methods.html>

Echo sounder measurements is a basic method to measure the ocean seafloor depth. It is therefore the basis for all subsequent geological, geophysical research works and theoretical developments. Many tectonic conclusions about the structure of the ocean floor depend, as mentioned above, on the idea of its relief, as reflected in various research papers: [12], [9], [10], [7], [8], [2]. In turn, it is closely related to the accuracy of bathymetric maps, the creation of which is subject to the methods of depth measurements. The echo-sounder recorders allowed measurement on the ship. Development of echo-sounder devices increased the number of measurements, improved their accuracy and expanded the scope of the research. In the late 1970-s the multi-beam sonar echo-sounder was invented. It opened a new opportunities for detailed study and mapping of the underwater topography. The special feature of the multi-beam echo sounders consists in the fact that the not one sound beam is sent to the ocean floor but many tens (or hundreds) of beams. The fan beams diverge from the emitter along the axis of the vessel, and enable the bathymetric survey of the seafloor with a wide band (from 70% of the depth to three or more depths – i.e., at the depth of 5000 m, a band of 15,000 m can be mapped). Currently, the multi-beam echo sounders of various designs (181-rays and more) are installed worldwide on approximately 1,000 vessels. Example of the one of the modern modifications of sounders created in Norway in the mid-90s, which measures ocean floor depth by 81 beams. The vertex angle of the radiation cone is about 120° , and the maximum width of the irradiation band is up to 3.5 depth. It is also equipped with a shallow-water echo sounder 1000, which is designed for offshore operations (average depth ca 200 m) and measures depths by 151 beams with a maximum matrix angle of up to 150° and a bandwidth of up to 7.4 depth [5]. Currently, the technical parameters of all modern echo sounders have been significantly improved. Schematic diagram of the multi-beam echo sounder consists of radiating and receiving antennas, subsystems radiation intake, control of onboard pitching and rolling sweeps, as well as numerous special blocks that allow to enter commands to do digital processing, to visualize bathymetry in the real-time.

Another method of the seafloor investigation is dredging. Dredging is a process that involves the aquatic excavation of water beds to remove sediments, pollutants, shellfish and other materials. A dredge is a machine that scoops or suctions rocks from the bottom of ocean. The methods and machinery used in dredging vary widely. The equipment set includes: a deep-water winch, a cable, a system for fastening the dredge and the actual dredge. A drag is a metal sampler with a triangular, rectangular or circular cross section intended to hold the rock. Dragging operation includes: identification of the sampling object, launching the vessel to that point, draining the dredge, actually dredging (detaching the rock from the substrate), and lifting the sample onboard.

Fig.5. Ocean floor dredging using two pipes. Image source:

https://pikabu.ru/story/dnougлубitelnyie_suda_dredgers_5528271

The total dredging time depends on the depth of the bottom, weather conditions. It can increase dramatically in the emergency cases or abnormal situations (e.g., difficult hooks). Most dredging is done by ships that tow a dredge along the ocean

floor. The hitch used by dredging is a clamping of the dredge on the ocean floor, which works as an anchor. The dredging time at depths of ca 5000 m is about 5 hours. The weight of the raised rocks can reach 100s of kg. One of the most important mechanisms for winding of the cable is a deep-water winch.

Chapter 4. Recommendations for the analysis of the current situation and further research

Nowadays Chinese government conducts a great variety of research and investigations in the coastal environments and marine geology of South China Sea region to support scientific understanding, develop tools and technology, and provide maps, data, and other information needed by resource managers and decision-makers [22], [23], [26]. Therefore, the progress and improvements in the development of marine geology program are clear and evident.

Fig.6. Ocean floor dredging using one pipe. Image source:
https://pikabu.ru/story/dnougubitelnyie_suda__dredgers_5528271

The coastal and marine geology program currently supported by Chinese government, shares a wide range of resources. many ways science supports the nation.

Fig.7. Geologic surveying: unloading the sample materials during dredging process:

https://pikabu.ru/story/dnougubitelnyie_suda_dredgers_5528271

Last but not least, besides scientific and research activities, it also includes popularization information for the Chinese citizens helping them to explain and illustrate scientific concepts of marine geology, scientific activities, expertise, technology, tools, and other educational resources concerning understanding of the ocean. Through newsletters, multimedia resources, special events, and other products, Chinese people can now learn more about the

Thus, recently, there are several clear points that have been successfully reached in developing Chinese marine geology program:

1. Well data equipped research centers focused on the marine geology across the coastal areas of the country (main centers: Qingdao, Hangzhou, Guangzhou, Xiamen and others) with established connections between machines, devices, sensors, and

people to link and communicate with each other, created collaboration, security, and high standards.

2. Information transparency, i.e. the ability of marine geo-information systems to model bathymetric world by enriching digital models with data get during ship cruises. This includes data analysis and provision of information.

3. Technical assistance: multi-beam data received during the ongoing cruises can provide geologists with GIS-assistance. The ability of GIS-assistance systems to support geologists by accumulation and storing GIS information comprehensibly in the research data centers to make informed decisions and solve urgent problems.

Currently, China Government has following goals in developing its marine geology program:

- Research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry
- Research on ocean and polar science and technology policies and institutions
- Fostering of outstanding professionals in the marine sector and public services
- Development, inspection, and repair of marine-related equipment, machinery, and technology
- Establishment and operation of marine infrastructure, such as marine science research stations
- Commissioned research, joint research, and technology partnerships with domestic and overseas universities, research institutions, and companies

Up to now, Chinese Government has been invested enormous financial and technological input, so the situation with advanced marine geology research in P.R.C. comparing to early 1950s is developed significantly, speed up by the great reforms and recent industrialization and computerization of China.

There are following several suggestions that can be given according to the current marine geology analysis in South China Sea region.

1. Regular off-shore geo-scientific studies and systematic high precision and accuracy mapping of the seafloor, both in exclusive economic zone and territorial waters along east and west coasts of South China Sea should be continued and maintained.
2. Regular sea expeditions should acquire geo-scientific data on the seabed sediments, seabed morphology, mineral resources, geochemistry, geophysical parameters, surface and subsurface samples and other geological data around the aquatory of South China Sea. A detailed documentation of all the seabed surface samples collected from the offshore cruises around South China Sea should be compiled into a regular set of publications to make possible create prognosis maps or evaluations. Combining long term heterogeneous satellite images and GIS data in marine resources prognosis mapping has great application potential, especially for the long term monitoring process.
2. In order to provide useful insight for marine geology management and gain correct content, in-situ data, received from the R/V expeditions has to be processed using advanced tools (analytics and algorithms) that can generate meaningful information on current situation of the marine geology in the South China Sea region. Thus, the big data center on marine geology structure around South China Sea has to be created. The data should be multi-source and actual.
2. Although the separated ocean-related organizations were integrated into one single agency, the coordination on developing and implementing oceans policy is essential. However, at the time of establishment of common marine research agencies, such as GEBCO bathymetric map, the coordination with other agencies is important. The suggestion therefore would be more transparent and easy cooperation between subordinated agencies focused on the marine research.
3. Establishment of the benefit-cost analysis would provide a framework for systematically assessing the efficiency of public policies accepted in marine geology. Therefore, the benefit-cost analysis should be applied before every new equipment is ordered, to assess pros and cons, advantages and possible financial drawbacks.

3. More often cross-functional discussions among geologists from all over the world, e.g. regular conferences, meetings, panels, etc, will help marine geology find the technology levers that are best suited to solve their particular problems. The selection of the most beneficial data is important for further geological prognosis. Correct and most recent technologies would deliver the most accurate results.

3. The specific need of South China Sea current marine geology research is first, to further widen international cooperation e.g. with Australia, the U.S and European countries, because geological issues have trans-border character and South China research should go beyond the Pacific Ocean region.

4. More close cooperation with neighboring countries of the areas near the South China Sea, such as Thailand, Philippine, Vietnam and Malaysia would be of great benefit for South China region further development of the marine program, because cooperation and sharing research have vast resources and long-term experience in marine geology issues, regular survey, including satellite based observations, and research.

5. Further development of seafloor mapping in the region of South China Sea. Seafloor maps are important tool to be used for location and navigation. Mapping the seafloor enables to know what can be found on the sea floor. Seafloor maps can help boaters located these types of habitat. Nowadays, mapping of the seafloor should be conducted using a multi-beam sonar system. This system consists of a transducer and a receiver mounted on the bottom of the ship. Therefore, the development of the precision of the seafloor mapping and enhancement of the cartographic precision is strongly recommended.

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